

Designing Singlet Fission Candidates from Donor-Acceptor Copolymers

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ABSTRACT

Singlet fission (SF) has demonstrated significant promise for boosting the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of solar cells. Traditionally, SF is targeted as an intermolecular process, however its dependence on crystal packing makes molecular design difficult. In contrast, intramolecular SF (iSF) enables the exploration of tunable bichromophoric systems following well-defined structure-property relationships. In this work, we propose a set of parameters to screen conjugated donor-acceptor copolymer candidates with potential iSF behavior. We focus our analysis on the $E(S_1) > 2E(T_1)$ thermodynamic condition and on the appropriate charge transfer (CT) character of S_1 . We map the CT character with respect to the frontier molecular orbital (FMO) energies of the constituent monomers, providing a cost-effective protocol for an accelerated screening of promising iSF donor-acceptor pairs, while minimizing the number of computations. These parameters are applied to a chemically diverse, curated library of 81 truncated dimers of synthetically feasible donor-acceptor copolymers. From our dataset, four candidates are flagged for iSF, two of which were previously experimentally reported. This protocol is envisioned to be scaled up for the high-throughput screening of large databases of donor-acceptor dimers for the design and identification of conjugated polymers capable of iSF.

1. Introduction

First described in 1965, singlet fission (SF) is the spin-allowed conversion of a high-energy singlet to two lower-energy triplets.¹ To be energetically possible, the excited singlet energy needs to be at least twice that of the triplet (*i.e.* $E(S_1) \geq 2E(T_1)$). By definition, SF is a multiexcitonic process: upon the absorption of light, the absorbing singlet splits into two independent triplets (T_1) through a correlated triplet-triplet pair (1TT) according to the following scheme:²

In organic photovoltaic devices, this theoretically leads to a doubled photocurrent if both excitons are separated at a donor-acceptor interface. In this way, materials exhibiting quantum efficiencies above 100% and power conversion efficiencies (PCE) beyond the thermodynamic (Shockley-Queisser) limit of 33% become accessible.³

Figure 1: Mechanisms for SF after absorption: direct S_1 to 1TT conversion following the blue arrows, or indirect conversion mediated by charge transfer (CT) states following the brown arrows.

SF involves two centers: following singlet excitation in one, there is energy transfer to the second, such that one triplet is formed at each center.² Both *direct*^{4,5} and *charge-transfer*⁶⁻⁹ mechanisms have been proposed for this (Figure 1). The formation of the triplet pair can proceed through either an intermolecular or an intramolecular process. In the former case, the centers are located on two separate molecules, while in the latter the two centers are covalently bound to one another. Intermolecular SF has been extensively studied in molecular crystals.^{1,10-13} However, its success depends highly on the coupling between the

separate units,¹⁴ which ultimately relies on the molecular packing, and as such can be difficult to predict and control.^{2,4} This limitation is circumvented in intramolecular SF (iSF).^{15,16} Such is the case of *covalently-linked dimers*, in which synthetic modification of the linking units enables fine-tuning of the spatial orientation between the sites.¹⁷⁻²⁰ However, precisely due to the proximity of the two implicated fragments, the triplets in these systems recombine quickly and rarely become independent. Molecules with extended conjugation, such as *polyenes* and *carotenoids*, have also shown iSF,²¹ but their large structural flexibility makes nonradiative decay pathways readily available.

A few studies have demonstrated iSF in *conjugated polymers*, particularly in donor-acceptor (D-A) copolymers, leading to some very promising candidates.²²⁻²⁶ On the one hand, Busby *et al.* designed a poly(benzodithiophene-*alt*-thiophene-1,1-dioxide) (BDT-TDO) copolymer with a triplet quantum yield of 170%, which highlighted the importance of i) strong intramolecular donor-acceptor interactions, and ii) an acceptor core with a low triplet energy. On the other hand, Zhai *et al.* reported SF character in thin films of poly(phenylene-*alt*-vinylene) albeit not in solution, indicating that for certain polymers SF may involve interchain processes.²⁴ Given the limited number of copolymer-based materials undergoing iSF reported so far, clear performance trends could not be established.

To date, research exploring the mechanisms of SF has been restricted to the small number of materials in which this process was experimentally observed.^{2,15,16,27} Computations of iSF in polymers have been done retroactively to rationalize SF reported in existing materials,^{22,28} but there has been a lack of effort to locate new iSF copolymer materials using computational tools.²⁹ Only very recently a computational screening of *intermolecular* SF candidates, based on crystal structures, has been reported.²⁷ Certainly, the discovery of novel iSF systems will largely benefit not only from large-scale screening but also from the development of new molecular design principles. In this work, we take advantage of the well-established modular chemistry of conjugated polymers, and their demonstrated potential for iSF, to explore their chemical space using

computational screening techniques. Through systematic modulation of the donor and acceptor units in truncated dimers, we sought to establish design rules that link the monomer and dimer characteristics to the iSF potential of the resulting copolymer. In this way, we provide an accelerated computational screening framework that allows to explore a wide range of potential conjugated copolymers from *in silico* donor-acceptor combinations. From a curated database of 81 systems, we identify four promising iSF candidates; in two of these iSF has been previously reported.^{22,25} Altogether, we discuss both the rational and large-scale strategies of molecular design that will enable the discovery of new iSF materials.

2. Methodology

2.1 Criteria to Achieve iSF and Design Strategy

The main conditions that SF candidates need to fulfill are the following: (1) the energy of S_1 is greater than or equal to twice the energy of T_1 : $E(S_1) \geq 2E(T_1)$;²⁹ (2) the coupling between the two chromophores involved is strong, to promote $S_1 \rightarrow {}^1TT$;¹⁵ and (3) the correlated triplet pair (1TT) must evolve into two independent triplets (T_1) that can physically separate from one another and escape recombination. These criteria are referred to here as the (1) *energetic*, (2) *coupling* and (3) *separation* criteria, respectively.

Figure 2: Fundamental design for strong donor-acceptor-type iSF polymers, in which absorption leading to S_1 on the strong donor (SD, in blue) provides enough charge transfer character (denoted with $\delta+$ and $\delta-$) to efficiently generate local T_1 on the adjacent strong acceptors (SA, in red).²²

Within the framework of donor-acceptor copolymers, the design strategy consists in combining a donor core,

which acts as the main photon absorption site and whose S_1 has a dominant CT contribution to the acceptor, with an acceptor featuring a low-lying triplet state (see **Figure 2**).²⁵ In this way, the strong CT character of S_1 is expected to promote an efficient splitting to 1TT (*coupling* criterion), while the spatial separation between the two triplets on nearby acceptors, separated by the donor unit, is expected to diminish the possibility of triplet-triplet recombination (*separation* criterion).

2.2 Database Construction

Our database includes nine donors and nine acceptors that are commonly found in the literature of conjugated polymers.³⁰⁻³⁴ These contain cyclic, fused, and bridged derivatives of thiophene, benzene, pyrrole, and other heterocycles (see **Figure 3**). Well-established chemical motifs were prioritized to ensure that potential SF candidates that emerge from this database are synthetically feasible, as well as units that are amenable to multiple polymerization techniques and that can be synthesized with high atom economy in few steps.³⁵⁻³⁷ Units reported in previous works to display iSF in conjugated polymers were included: thiophene-1,1-dioxide (TDO)²⁵, benzodithiophene (BDT)²³, phenylene²⁴, vinylene²⁴ (in the form of (E)-2-(2-(thiophen-2-yl)vinyl)thiophene), TTV,²⁴ cyclopentadithiophene (CPDT)²², benzothiadiazole (BT)²² and isoindigo (ii).²⁶

Each donor and acceptor core was encoded as a SMILES string.³⁸ The dimer set was generated by linking the nine donors with the nine acceptors through a covalent carbon-carbon bond to form the 81 donor-acceptor pairs. The resulting SMILES strings of the dimer were then converted to Cartesian coordinates by using the gen3d operation in OpenBabel,³⁹ which includes a conformational search and a geometry optimization at the force field level. Tighter convergence criteria were then applied by reoptimizing the geometries at the density functional theory (DFT) level. The full method used for dataset construction is detailed in section S1 of the Supporting Information, and all data are made available in the Materials Cloud repository.

Figure 3: Library of acceptors and donors. Dotted lines denote the bonding positions for D-A polymer chains. Common abbreviations for the cores, when available, are given in parentheses. Structures discussed in section 3.1 are highlighted in red and blue.

2.3 Computational Details

DFT computations were performed by using the Gaussian16 package (Revision A.03).⁴⁰ Ground and excited state geometries for the model copolymer described in section 3.1 were optimized at the ω B97X-D/TZVP level of theory. The 6-31G* basis set was used for subsequent database computations as it was shown to give very similar results to TZVP (see section S2). Normal mode analysis confirmed that the stationary points were minima with all real frequencies. To evaluate the *energetic* criterion, vertical excitations and excited-state geometry optimizations were computed by using time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT), within the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDA) to correct for the triplet instabilities reported in TD-DFT.⁴¹ The range-separated hybrid functional ω B97X-D was used, given its accurate treatment of excited states, in particular with respect to its

description of charge transfer (CT) character.^{42,43} The default range separation parameter ($\omega=0.2$) was used as this has been found to be the optimal value for conjugated systems of similar size to the present dimers.^{44,45} Full details of functional and basis set benchmarking are given in section S2. For computations with solvent, the solvent cavity reaction field (SCRFF) was used with a conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM), which was found to give nearly equivalent results to the SMD continuum model (see section S2.3 for a comparison of solvent models).

Gaussian output files were parsed with cclib⁴⁶ and TheoDORÉ (version 1.7.2)^{47,48} to assess the *coupling* and *separation* criteria by means of the local and CT character of the electronic transitions. This is done through the $\Omega_{i \rightarrow j}$ values, which quantify the amount of hole (h^+) and electron (e^-) transition density located in the different molecular fragments (i,j). In the

present case, we considered two fragments: the donor (D) and the acceptor (A) cores of the donor-acceptor dimer. Accordingly, the electronic transition is decomposed into a matrix containing four Ω values, in which the diagonal elements ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow D}$ and $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}$) quantify intrafragment contributions (*i.e.* the hole and electron are formed on the same fragment, $i=j$), while the off-diagonal elements are the charge-transfer components ($i \neq j$), in which the electron density is transferred from the donor fragment to the acceptor fragment ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}$) or vice versa ($\Omega_{A \rightarrow D}$). For each transition, the sum of the four Ω values is 1.

3. Results

The results are presented in four sections. In section 3.1 we analyze the excited state characteristics of the BDT-TDO copolymer, which previously exhibited iSF experimentally. In sections 3.2 and 3.3 we establish specific numerical thresholds to efficiently screen the *energetic*, *coupling* and *separation* criteria (section 2.1) from a curated dataset of 81 donor-acceptor dimers (section 2.2). Finally, in section 3.4 we map the CT character of S_1 with respect to the frontier molecular orbital (FMO) energies of the constituent monomers, and test it on 25 substituted bithiophene-benzothiadiazole pairs.

3.1 BDT-TDO Copolymer

Copolymers made of thiophene-1,1-dioxide (TDO, shown in red in **Figure 3**) acceptors, and benzodithiophene (BDT, shown in blue in **Figure 3**) donors have shown good SF quantum yields and triplet pair lifetimes.²⁵ Being a prototypical SF copolymer with excellent properties, we selected it as a representative test-case to establish a cost-effective computational strategy to evaluate iSF design criteria (section 2.1).

Vertical and adiabatic S_1 , T_1 , T_2 , and Q_1 energies were computed using the dimer (D-A) and tetramer (D-A-D-A) cluster models of the BDT-TDO copolymer (see **Table S4**). While the *energetic* criterion (1) is not fulfilled for the dimer model at the Franck-Condon point ($\Delta E_{ST}^{vert} = E(S_1) - 2E(T_1) = -0.72$ eV), this value becomes much closer to zero in the adiabatic picture ($\Delta E_{ST}^{adiab} = -0.18$ eV), and even slightly positive for the extended tetramer model

($\Delta E_{ST}^{adiab} = 0.04$ eV). This highlights the impact of adiabaticity in predicting potential SF behavior, while showing that the dimer-to-tetramer extension has a much less meaningful impact on the energetic criterion.

Fragment-based decomposition analysis of hole and electron density in the excited states revealed that charge transfer from the donor core (BDT) to the acceptor (TDO) at the Franck-Condon point is the primary contribution to the S_1 excitation ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1} = 0.46$), following the *coupling* criterion, whereas a local excitation within the acceptor dominates in T_1 state ($\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1} = 0.42$), matching with the *separation* criterion (see section 2.1).⁴⁹ Similar values were obtained for the adiabatic states and, in all cases, the three other possible contributions to excitation character are smaller (see **Tables S5-S6**).

To be efficient, SF needs to overcome triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA) paths, that is, recombination of the two T_1 states to higher excited states such as T_2 or Q_1 . For the recombination paths to be energetically unfavourable, both $E(T_2) - 2E(T_1)$ and $E(Q_1) - 2E(T_1)$ should be positive.¹⁵ While low-lying T_2 or Q_1 states do not necessarily prevent the singlet splitting, they may reduce the rate of SF. The computed adiabatic energy of T_2 resulted in 0.4 eV below S_1 when evaluated in gas phase conditions. Remarkably, this difference is significantly reduced to 0.1 eV when including polar solvent effects (see **Table S4**). This decrease originates in the strong CT character of S_1 , which has negligible contributions to the mainly local T_1 and T_2 states. Finally, we found that Q_1 is consistently above both S_1 and T_2 in all cases.

In summary, our computations correctly predict (1) thermodynamic adequacy, (2) donor-to-acceptor CT character as the largest contribution to S_1 , and (3) T_1 being primarily localized on the acceptor in the BDT-TDO copolymer. Adiabaticity plays an important role in the ΔE_{ST} prediction and thus, empirical rules to correct cost-effective vertical energies of D-A dimers are required. In the next section, we exploit this approach using a curated database of D-A dimers.

Figure 4: ΔE_{ST}^{vert} and ΔE_{ST}^{adiab} values associated with the 81 donor-acceptor dimers, colored based on the acceptor. These are computed with TDDFT (TDA) at the ω B97X-D/6-31G* level. The vertical and adiabatic cutoffs established as energy conservation criterion are shown as dotted lines at -1.0 and 0.0 eV, respectively.

3.2 Excited States Energies

Threshold for the energetic criterion. We sought to establish a computationally efficient method to evaluate ΔE_{ST} (i.e. the *energetic* criterion), which bypasses the structural optimization of S_1 and T_1 . To do so, the S_1 and T_1 energies of 81 donor-acceptor dimers in our dataset (see section 2.2) were evaluated at the S_0 geometry and at their excited state minima to establish an empirical trend. We found that the relationship between the vertical and adiabatic energies for both S_1 and T_1 is linear (see **Figures S9** and **S10**), and thus the correlation between the vertical and adiabatic ΔE_{ST} is also linear (see **Figures 4** and **S11**). The vertical T_1 energies are found to be consistently higher than those obtained from adiabatic computations. As a result, all dimers with $\Delta E_{ST} \geq 0$ eV in adiabatic computations are also above -1 eV when computed vertically (shown as dotted lines in **Figure 4**). It is therefore possible to approximate the energy conservation criterion computed adiabatically to:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{adiab} \geq 0 \text{ eV} \leftrightarrow \Delta E_{ST}^{vert} \geq -1 \text{ eV}$$

In this way, all the systems with $\Delta E_{ST}^{vert} \geq -1$ will be selected as potentially promising for iSF. This provides a simple and cheap method to estimate ΔE_{ST}

from vertical computations by means of systematically shifting the threshold value corresponding to the *energetic* criterion. It is noted that the linear relationship between the vertical and adiabatic values fails when ΔE_{ST}^{vert} is below -2 eV. However, this will not bias our identification of potential iSF candidates based on this criterion, as this loss of correlation occurs well below the established threshold of -1 eV.

The computed ΔE_{ST}^{vert} and ΔE_{ST}^{adiab} values of the 81 D-A dimers are represented with respect to their acceptor unit in **Figure 4**. Considering the nine sets of same-acceptor pairs, the dimers can be classified into two categories: those in which the *energetic* criterion mainly depends on the acceptor unit (*acceptor-dependent*), and those which have a broad distribution of ΔE_{ST} depending on both the donor and acceptor constituents (*donor-tuning*). In the former category, all dimers containing the same acceptor (DPP, iI, TDO and NDI) have approximately the same energy splitting values regardless of the donor. In the latter category are the dimers containing BT, F4, TPD, bithiazole, and BDO acceptors, for which certain donors modulate the excited state energy levels toward favorable splitting. In particular, the donors TVT, CPDT, 2,2'-bithiophene, thienothiophene and BDT, which all include

thiophene moieties, shift ΔE_{ST} to more positive values, while the donors that do not have thiophene motifs (Cbz, fluorene and phenylene) are systematically detrimental to the energy conservation condition. Smaller values of ΔE_{ST} originate in nonplanar dihedral angles between the donor and acceptor units in dimers linked via a benzene ring. This leads to a weaker effective conjugation and, generally, to higher T_1 excitation energies (see section S5).

To assess whether dimer models are representative of larger oligomeric (and polymeric) systems, we evaluated (i) the vertical and adiabatic excited state energies, (ii) the structure, and (iii) the excited state character, of a subset of 21 tetramers. We considered systems that span the entire range of excitation energies and Ω values, with each donor and acceptor moiety represented at least once. The correlation between the dimer and tetramer vertical excitation energies is linear for the entire range of excitation energies and the y-intercept is close to zero (see

Figures S15-S16). Consequently, negligible deviations in ΔE_{ST}^{vert} and ΔE_{ST}^{adiab} between the two cluster models are obtained (see **Figures S17-S18**). Also, the excited states' character remains very similar in the vertical and adiabatic pictures for both the dimer (**Figure S12 and S13**) and tetramer models (see **Figures S19-S22**), likely due to the small changes in D-A conjugation upon excited state geometry optimization (see **Figures S23-S25**). A comparison of the S_0 and S_1 minima structures for the dimer and tetramer models can be found in section S7. Note that two of the 81 cases deviate significantly from the vertical versus adiabatic $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ trend (**Figure S12**). This indicates that the vertical approach may not always be valid for evaluating $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$, while the iSF potential of donor-acceptor polymeric systems in terms of ΔE_{ST} and $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ can be efficiently captured through vertical excitation computations on D-A model dimers.

Figure 5: Adiabatic donor-to-acceptor charge-transfer contribution of S_1 ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$) and vertical local acceptor contribution of T_1 ($\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$) obtained for the 81 dimers, colored based on the acceptor. Evaluated with TheoDORE using results from computations with TDDFT (TDA) at the ω B97X-D/6-31G* level.

3.3 Excited State Character

To identify how the excitation energies and thus, ΔE_{ST} , are affected by the different state character of S_1 and T_1 , we performed a fragment-based analysis of the main local and CT contributions. We focused on the donor-to-acceptor CT component of S_1 ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$) and on the local acceptor contribution of T_1 ($\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$) as key requirements for efficient iSF that will potentially favour singlet splitting and prevent fast TTA, respectively (criteria 2 and 3, section 2.1). These are represented for the 81 dimers in **Figure 5**. The dimers BDT-TDO (discussed in section 3.1) and CPDT-BT, for which iSF has been reported,^{22,25} fulfill both criteria, with the key contributions ($\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ and $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$) both above 0.4. The reported bithiophene-iI system²⁶ fulfills the *separation* criterion with $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ above 0.4, but not the *coupling* criterion as it is characterized by a small $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ of 0.1. For that reason, we tentatively select a $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ of 0.4 as threshold for screening purposes and classify the remaining systems according to their $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$. Remarkably, with the exception of one BDO-containing dimer, all other dimers found in the $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1} > 0.4$ region have BT as acceptor, which systematically generates very promising candidates for iSF. In fact, the classification into *acceptor-dependent* and *donor-tuning* D-A dimers discussed for the energy splitting values remains valid for $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ and $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$. In particular, DPP- and iI- dimers, which systematically show positive ΔE_{ST} , lead to large $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T_1}$ and small $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ in all cases (due to large $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ values). Despite fulfilling the energetic criterion, the fact that S_1 and T_1 are both characterized by a local excitation in the acceptor (or the donor) may be detrimental to the D-A design strategy for iSF. As a consequence, the dimers involving these acceptors may not undergo efficient iSF, but most likely interchain SF based on local acceptor states. Large singlet-triplet energy splitting has been previously associated with local excitations in organic systems.⁵⁰ However, new design principles need to be considered when evaluating the iSF capabilities of D-A copolymers. From our results, it is possible to envision a ‘modular’ design strategy based on the frontier molecular orbital (FMO) energies of the

donor and acceptor units to screen the CT or local character of S_1 in the dimer.

3.4 Charge Transfer Prediction

In this section, we correlate the CT character of S_1 in the 81 D-A dimers with the FMOs of the 18 constituent monomers (collected in **Table S7**). This is represented schematically in **Figure 6**, where it is

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the dependence of $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ in the dimer with the FMOs (HOMO, LUMO) of the monomers. The local excitations in the donor (blue) and acceptor (red) compete with the CT excitation (green).

shown how the CT excitation (D→A) competes with local excitations in either the donor or the acceptor depending on the relative ordering of the monomer FMOs. Within this approximation, the ratio between the local orbital gaps and the resulting CT energy difference defined as

$$\frac{A_{LUMO} - A_{HOMO}}{A_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}} \text{ and } \frac{D_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}}{A_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}}$$

will estimate favorable (>1) or unfavorable (<1) CT excitations with respect to local excitations. Both ratios above 1 indicate that the FMOs of the monomers will align in such a way that the D-A dimer HOMO originates from the donor monomer and the LUMO from the acceptor monomer. This will favor low-lying CT excitations in the dimer. In contrast, if the first (second) ratio is below 1, the monomer FMOs will be positioned such that both FMOs of the D-A dimer will originate from the acceptor (donor) monomer FMOs. If this occurs, it is expected that the low-lying excited states in the dimer will be

dominated by local excitations in the acceptor (donor) core, thus disfavoring CT. Both ratios are therefore necessary to describe the relative positions of the monomer FMOs. The approximation of considering orbital gaps as one-electron transitions is possible because the relationship with the local excited energies is rather linear (see **Figures S26-S27**). This shows that the exciton binding energy, defined as the difference between the orbital gap and the excitation energies, is relatively constant for all donors and acceptors considered.

Figure 7 associates the computed FMO ratios with the computed $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ values. It can be seen that the donor-acceptor monomer pairs with FMOs best suited for CT are located above 1.0 in both axes. In contrast, dimers with FMO ratios below 1 correctly predict minor CT character ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1} < 0.2$). This numerical comparison using monomer FMO energies is therefore a robust metric for eliminating poor potential iSF candidates.

To illustrate the direct impact of monomer FMO energies on $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$, we generated 25 substituted bithiophene-BT donor-acceptor pairs. The monomer energy levels are substantially modulated through functionalization of the conjugated backbone with electron-donating (-OH), electron-withdrawing (-CN) and halide (-F, -Cl) moieties. As a result, the CT character of S_1 in the dimer ($\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1} = 0.44$ when unsubstituted) becomes as low as 0.26 when an electron-withdrawing group is placed on the donor unit, and as high as 0.75 when electron-donating (withdrawing) groups are attached to the donor (acceptor) moiety. These variations are correctly captured by the FMO ratio model (**Figure 7**), which reproduces the general increase of $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S_1}$ as the FMO ratios increase. This example demonstrates that monomer functionalization can be used to optimize the properties necessary for iSF.

Figure 7: (top) FMO ratios of the 81 donor-acceptor monomer pairs included in our dataset (see section 2.2), and (bottom) of 25 substituted bithiophene-BT monomer pairs. Cutoffs for discarding poor CT dimers are represented by

the dotted lines. The structures of the reference (nonsubstituted) dimer and the dimers with the highest and lowest $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ values are shown. In both plots, the $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ of the resulting dimer is given by the color gradient.

4. Screening protocol

The protocol established to evaluate and screen promising iSF candidates among donor-acceptor copolymers consists of the following steps:

Step 1. Compute the ground state FMOs of all donor and acceptor monomer cores, and evaluate the FMO ratios for the donor-acceptor monomer pairs according to the expressions

$$\frac{D_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}}{A_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}} > 1 \text{ and } \frac{A_{LUMO} - A_{HOMO}}{A_{LUMO} - D_{HOMO}} > 1$$

Step 2. For the candidate donor-acceptor combinations resulting from step 1, generate the dimers and compute the vertical S_1 and T_1 excited state energies. Apply the energetic criterion associated with vertical energies:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{vert} \geq -1 \text{ eV}$$

Step 3. Determine the character of the vertical T_1 state and apply the *separation* criterion following the Ω values:

$$\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T1} \geq 0.4$$

Step 4. Optimize the S_1 state and classify the systems according to the *coupling* criterion $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$.

The computations of the different steps consist in ground state (step 1), vertical excitations (steps 2 and 3), and adiabatic optimizations (step 4), while structures larger than dimers are not required. It is worth emphasizing that step 1 significantly reduces the number of computations from $N_D \cdot N_A$ to $N_D + N_A$

(where N_D is number of donors and N_A is number of acceptors). To illustrate the efficiency of this protocol in filtering candidates, we apply it to the dataset of 81 dimers generated in this work (section 2.2). First, 19 possible combinations (representing 23% of the dataset) would be eliminated in step 1 and would not require dimer excited state computations. Then, 42 dimers (52%) would be rejected in step 2. From the remaining 20 systems, 14 fulfill $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T1} \geq 0.4$ in step 3 and therefore require further adiabatic optimizations in step 4. The $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ values of these final 14 systems (17%) are shown in **Figure 8**. The systems previously reported to undergo iSF (BDT-TDO and CPDT-BT),^{22,25} are classified as the most promising ones, and two new promising candidates, thieno[3,2-b]thiophene-BT and 2,2'-bithiophene-BT are predicted. While they exhibit less CT character than these top four candidates, six other TDO-containing dimers (marked in blue) are also flagged for promising iSF character. Interestingly, the iSF isoindigo system (bithiophene-iI) reported in ref. 26 is discarded in our protocol. While it fulfills $\Delta E_{ST}^{vert} \geq -1 \text{ eV}$ and $\Omega_{A \rightarrow A}^{T1} \geq 0.4$, it has a $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ value of < 0.1 . To ensure that our predictions for this system are reliable, we re-evaluated $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ with alternative methods but similar values are obtained (section S9). In comparison with our reference BDT-TDO system that exhibits iSF in the ultrafast scale ($< 1 \text{ ps}$),²⁵ bithiophene-iI displays iSF after 60 ps,²⁶ which is in the range of timescales observed for other SF materials.⁵¹ Further investigations are therefore needed to determine the iSF mechanism of D-A copolymers characterized by small $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ values, particularly those containing the iI acceptor, such as bithiophene-iI and the iI-containing materials marked in green in Figure 8.

Figure 8: (left) Compounds retained following steps 1-3 of the screening protocol, ordered following the ranking criterion of $\Omega_{D \rightarrow A}^{S1}$ as defined in step 4 and colored based on acceptor. (right) The best four potential DA copolymer candidates flagged for iSF.

5. Conclusions

We have developed a cost-effective computational protocol to perform large-scale screening of donor-acceptor copolymers with promising features for intramolecular singlet-fission. Using a structurally diverse database of donor and acceptor units, we have established a simplified yet robust computational strategy to evaluate the energy splitting criterion and the charge-transfer requirements of the D-A candidates from conventional vertical excited state computations. In the context of accelerated screening, we have proposed an expression to predict the excited state character of D-A dimers from the FMO energies of their constituent donor and acceptor units. This drastically reduces computational time in initial screening stages, as the number of computations is reduced from $N_D \cdot N_A$ to $N_D + N_A$, N_D and N_A being the number of donor and acceptors considered.

This protocol is based on the main characteristics of two donor-acceptor pairs that exhibit singlet fission behavior experimentally,^{22,25} and we propose two promising new candidates, thieno[3,2-b]thiophene-BT and 2,2'-bithiophene-BT, that have not been studied to date. Benzothiadiazole (BT) and thiophene-1,1-dioxide (TDO) in particular show promise as acceptor units which drive iSF in D-A materials. Altogether, these findings pave the way for high-throughput screening of large, chemically

diverse databases of D-A conjugated polymers as a mean to bolster the collective library of SF materials.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Details of database construction, benchmarking results, and supplementary figures pertaining to excited state character, tetramers, monomer properties and excitonic effects are made available in the Supporting Information.

DATASET

All data (dimer excitation energies and state character, monomer FMO energies and excitation energies, substituted monomer FMO energies, and substituted dimer excitation energies and state character) are available in a Materials Cloud repository (10.24435/materialscloud:z8-ve). The collection of all output files from Gaussian, Turbomole and TheoDORÉ computations is available at the same location.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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